

1 Isotopic and *in situ* DRIFTS study of the CO₂ methanation 2 mechanism using Ni/CeO₂ and Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts.

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15 16 **Abstract**

17
18 The CO₂ methanation reaction mechanism has been studied for Ni/CeO₂ and Ni/Al₂O₃
19 catalysts. For both catalysts, isotopic experiments evidence a dynamic equilibrium
20 between gas phase CO₂ and catalyst oxygen, consisting of CO₂ chemisorption,
21 exchange of CO₂ oxygens with the catalysts, and CO₂ desorption. In the presence of
22 H₂, part of the chemisorbed CO₂ is desorbed after oxygens exchange and part is
23 hydrogenated. The higher methanation activity and 100% CH₄ selectivity of Ni/CeO₂ is
24 attributed to the following mechanistic aspects: i) XPS characterization shows that
25 Ni/CeO₂ combines two types of active sites efficient for CO₂ dissociation at the NiO-
26 Ceria interface and for H₂ dissociation on reduced Ni⁰ particles; ii) pulse experiments
27 show that water desorption is the slowest step of the mechanism, and, due to the high
28 oxygen mobility throughout the ceria lattice, water is not necessarily formed on the
29 same active sites that chemisorb CO₂, that is, the CO₂ chemisorption sites at the NiO-
30 CeO₂ interface are not blocked by water molecules; iii) *in situ* DRIFTS experiments
31 show that the Ni/CeO₂ surface does not accumulate carbon-containing species under
32 reaction conditions, which allows faster chemisorption and dissociation of CO₂. The
33 handicaps of the Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst, in comparison to Ni/CeO₂, are: i) There are not
34 specific active sites for H₂ dissociation, and molecular H₂ must reduce surface species;
35 ii) all the steps of the mechanism take place on the same active sites, and the slow
36 release of water and the accumulation of surface formates on these sites delay the
37 chemisorption of further CO₂ molecules. The formation of formates as reaction
38 intermediates results in the production of CO as undesired byproduct, since part of the
39 formates are totally hydrogenated to CH₄ but part decompose yielding CO+H₂O.

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41
42 **Keywords:** CO₂ methanation; nickel; ceria; metal-support interaction; mechanism; isotope.

43 1.- INTRODUCTION.

44

45 Substitution of fossil fuels by clean energy sources is one of the main worldwide
46 challenges to face the problem of global warming. H₂ obtained by renewable energies
47 will probably be an important energy vector in the future and for that reason, suitable H₂
48 storage and transportation technologies are being developed.

49 One of the options is CO₂ hydrogenation to yield CH₄, which is known as
50 Sabatier's reaction or CO₂ methanation reaction. CH₄ can be stored and transported
51 more easily than H₂ using the already available infrastructures used for natural gas. In
52 addition, this process contributes to mitigate the emission of CO₂ to the atmosphere if
53 the energy used both for H₂ production and for acceleration of the Sabatier's reaction
54 comes from renewable sources.

55 From a thermodynamic point of view the methanation reaction is exothermic,
56 but kinetics at low temperature are not favorable because both CO₂ and H₂ molecules
57 are quite stable and an important energy barrier must be overcome to break their
58 bonds. In addition, the CO₂-H₂ reaction can yield different reaction products, such as
59 CO, different hydrocarbons, alcohols, etc, and selectivity towards CH₄ is necessary in
60 this case. Several catalysts have demonstrated to accelerate CO₂ and H₂ dissociation,
61 and to favor the formation of methane as main reaction product. These catalysts
62 include nickel [1-7] and novel metals (ruthenium [8-15], palladium [16-18] and rhodium
63 [19-22]), the former being a promising option for practical use due to the lower price.

64 Two reaction mechanisms have been proposed to describe the catalytic
65 hydrogenation of CO₂ [23], the so-called associative mechanism and the dissociative
66 mechanism. They mainly differ on the pathway for chemisorption and dissociation of
67 the CO₂ molecules. In the associative mechanism, CO₂ is molecularly chemisorbed,
68 and CO₂ oxygens are removed by H₂ afterwards in two consecutive steps. On the
69 contrary, in the dissociative mechanism the CO₂ molecules dissociate upon

70 chemisorption, yielding a surface carbonyl and an oxygen atom that reacts with H₂
71 afterwards.

72 The type of CO₂ methanation mechanism depends on the catalyst, and
73 understanding the reaction pathways taking place is necessary for further design better
74 catalysts. It has been reported [24] that CeO₂-supported Ni catalysts are more active
75 and selective towards CH₄ formation than Ni catalysts supported on Al₂O₃, TiO₂ and
76 MgO, but the mechanisms responsible of these differences have not been studied in
77 detail. Also, Ni/Ce_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O₂ has been reported [25] to be more active than Ni/γ-Al₂O₃,
78 and differences in the type of surface CO₂ species were detected upon CO₂
79 chemisorption in the absence of H₂.

80 The goal of this article is to study differences in the role of the CeO₂ and Al₂O₃
81 supports in the Ni-catalyzed CO₂ methanation reaction, and isotopic C¹⁸O₂ experiments
82 and in situ DRIFTS reactions have been carried out for this purpose.

83

84 **2.- EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS.**

85

86 **2.1. Catalysts preparation.**

87 Two catalysts have been prepared and used in this study, which are referred as
88 Ni/CeO₂ and Ni/Al₂O₃. Commercial γ-Al₂O₃ was supplied by Alfa Aesar (Stock n°
89 43855) and CeO₂ was prepared by calcination of cerium citrate at 600 °C for 6 hours.
90 Cerium citrate was prepared by precipitation using an ethanolic solution of
91 Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O (99.5%, Alfa Aesar) and citric acid (99%, Sigma-Aldrich) in
92 stoichiometric proportions. Nickel was loaded by incipient wetness impregnation using
93 a Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (Sigma-Aldrich) ethanolic solution. The catalysts were calcined at 600
94 °C in static air for 6 hour using a heating rate of 5 °C/min. The target Ni content was 8.5
95 w/w %.

96

97

98

99 2.2. Catalysts characterization.

100

101 The nickel content was determined by ICP-OES after the catalyst were
102 completely dissolved in a HCl + HNO₃ mixture (3:1 in volume), being assisted by
103 microwaves.

104 X-ray diffractograms were obtained in a Rigaku Miniflex II diffractometer using
105 CuK_α radiation ($\lambda = 0.155418$ nm) between 10° and 90° 2 θ angles, with a step of
106 0.025°.

107 N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms were measured at -196 °C in an Autosorb-6
108 device, from Quantachrome, after outgassing the catalysts under vacuum at 150 °C for
109 2 h.

110 H₂-TPR characterization was carried out in a Micromeritics Pulse ChemiSorb
111 2705 device, using 40 ml/min of 5% H₂/Ar flow. 40 mg of catalyst were loaded on a
112 tubular quartz reactor coupled to a TCD detector, and the temperature was raised from
113 room temperature to 950 °C at 10 °C/min.

114 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) characterization was carried out in a K-
115 ALPHA Thermo Scientific device (Al-K α radiation; 1486.6 eV), using an X-ray spot with
116 400 μ m diameter, 3 mA and 12 kV. The binding energy scale was calibrated by setting
117 the C1s peak at 284.6 eV. XPS characterization was made to both the pretreated and
118 used catalysts.

119

120 2.3. Catalytic tests.

121 Catalytic tests were performed in a fixed-bed 9 mm inner diameter cylindrical
122 reactor using 400 mg of catalyst mixed with quartz particles (1-1.25 mm). The bed
123 volume was 1 cm³ and the GHSV was 12000 h⁻¹. The gas composition was monitored

124 with a gas chromatograph (Agilent HP7890B). The catalyst was pre-treated at 500 °C
125 for 1 hour under 20% H₂/He (200 cm³ min⁻¹), and after cooling to 200 °C in inert gas,
126 the reaction mixture (16 % CO₂ + 64 % H₂ and He balance) was fed with a total
127 flowrate of 200 ml/min. The temperature was raised to 450 °C in steps of 25 ° C, with a
128 heating rate of 5 ° C/min between steps, and the gas composition was measured in
129 each step under steady state conditions.

130

131 **2.4. Isotopic experiments.**

132 Isotopic experiments were carried out with ¹³C¹⁸O₂ (Aldrich; 99% ¹³C, 95% ¹⁸O)
133 pulses, in a cylindrical reactor (inner diameter 4 mm) coupled to a mass spectrometer
134 Pfeiffer Vacuum (model OmniStar) operating at 1 second frequency. The catalyst (50
135 mg) was pretreated in 50 % H₂/He (20 ml/min) at 500 °C for 60 minutes, and then the
136 temperature was stabilized at 350 °C under the same gas flow, which was kept for the
137 whole experiment. A six-way valve with a loop of 100 µl was used, which was filled at 9
138 psi with the gas to be pulsed. This volume of gas is dragged by the main gas stream
139 once the position of the valve is changed. Three Ar pulses were first fed, and
140 afterwards, three pulses of ¹²C¹⁶O₂ followed by three pulses of ¹³C¹⁸O₂. The pulses were
141 fed in intervals of 7 minutes, which allows stabilization of all m/z signals after the
142 previous pulse.

143

144 **2.5. *In situ* DRIFTS experiments.**

145 *In situ* DRIFTS experiments were performed in an infrared spectrometer Jasco,
146 model FT/IR-4100 using a reaction cell for temperature and reaction gas control. The
147 cell was designed to allow the gas flow through the catalytic bed (70 mg of undiluted
148 catalyst). The catalyst was pretreated in 50% H₂/He at 450 °C for 60 minutes, and then
149 was cooled down to room temperature under H₂/He mixture. The background spectrum
150 was recorded in He, and then, the methanation mixture (16 % CO₂ + 64 % H₂ and He
151 balance) was fed and the temperature was raised up to 450 °C in steps of 50 °C.

152 Spectra were recorded after 60 minutes in isothermal conditions at each temperature
 153 from 4000 to 1000 cm^{-1} with a step of 1 cm^{-1} .

154 3.- RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

155

156 3.1. Catalysts characterization by N_2 adsorption, XRD and H_2 -TPR.

157

158 Figure 1 shows the N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms recorded at -196°C , and
 159 the BET specific surface areas determined from these isotherms are included in Table
 160 1.

161

162

Figure 1. N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms at -196°C .

163

164

165 Table 1. Results of the catalysts characterization by ICP and N_2 adsorption.

166

	Ni (wt. %)	BET specific surface area (m^2/g)
$\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$	9.4	172
Ni/CeO_2	8.2	10

167

168

169 N₂ uptake is significantly higher for Ni/Al₂O₃ than for Ni/CeO₂, which is
170 consistent with the BET values (172 vs 10 m²/g, respectively). The shape of the
171 Ni/Al₂O₃ isotherm combines rapid N₂ uptake at very low relative pressure, which could
172 be related with the presence of micropores, with smooth uptake at intermediate
173 pressures and a hysteresis loop above P/P₀ = 0.5 that evidences the presence of
174 mesopores. This type of porosity is characteristic of the commercial γ -Al₂O₃ support
175 used in the preparation of this catalyst. The low porosity of the Ni/CeO₂ catalyst is also
176 expected due to CeO₂ support being prepared by calcination of citrates. Despite the
177 low surface area, this material has been selected because optimizes the NiO-CeO₂
178 contact for the CO₂ methanation reaction, which requires an optimum proportion of
179 actives sites for CO₂ and H₂ dissociation, as was observed in unpublished results of
180 our group.

181 The crystalline phases were studied by XRD, and the diffractograms of the two
182 catalysts are included in Figure 2.

183
184

Figure 2. X-Ray diffractograms of the catalysts.

185

186 The Ni/CeO₂ catalyst shows peaks attributed to CeO₂ (JCPDS 00-034-0394)
187 and NiO (JCPDS 01-075-0269) [26, 27], and the Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst shows peaks of the
188 γ -Al₂O₃ phase [28]. CeO₂ crystallizes in fluorite structure, with main peaks at 28.5, 33.1,
189 47.6, and 56.5°, and these peaks are sharper than those of the γ -Al₂O₃ phase. The
190 broad peaks of γ -Al₂O₃ are consistent with the low crystallinity of this phase. The tiny
191 peaks of the cubic structure of NiO at 37.5, 43.4 and 63.0° are properly identified in the
192 Ni/CeO₂ diffractogram, but are not so obvious in that of Ni/Al₂O₃. This is, in part,
193 because some NiO and γ -Al₂O₃ peaks appear at similar angles, and the broad γ -Al₂O₃
194 peaks mask the tiny peaks of NiO. However, the intensity of the (200) NiO peak at
195 43.4°, which is observed in both diffractograms, is much better defined in that of
196 Ni/CeO₂, and this suggests that NiO crystals are smaller on Ni/Al₂O₃ than on Ni/CeO₂.
197 Quantitative comparison of the NiO crystallite sizes is not possible because the
198 crystallite size cannot be obtained for Ni/Al₂O₃. The smaller crystals of NiO on γ -Al₂O₃
199 can be attributed to the better dispersion due to higher surface area of the γ -Al₂O₃
200 support with regard to CeO₂.

201 The redox properties of the catalysts was studied by H₂-TPR experiments, and
202 the reduction profiles are shown in Figure 3. Reduction of the Ni/CeO₂ catalyst takes
203 place at much lower temperature than Ni/Al₂O₃ reduction, as expected, showing
204 several reduction events. On the one hand, a small sharp peak is observed at 250 °C,
205 with small shoulders at lower temperature that can be assigned to NiO reduction [24].
206 The amount of H₂ consumed has been calculated and it is estimated that only 1.6 % of
207 the total amount of NiO loaded on the catalyst has been reduced in this event. On the
208 other hand, a large peak appears at 345 °C with a shoulder at higher temperature,
209 corresponding the amount of H₂ consumed to a 122% of NiO available, i.e., not only
210 NiO is being reduced in this event but also part of surface CeO₂. Moreover, a third
211 peak is observed at 810 °C related to the reduction of bulk ceria.

212 In the case of Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst, the reduction starts at 500 °C and a main peak
213 is observed at 825°C with two shoulders at 725 and 600 °C. The total amount of H₂
214 consumed is that required for 100% NiO reduction to Ni⁰. Al₂O₃-supported NiO has
215 been reported to be reduced in three events [29, 30], which is consistent with the
216 shape of the Ni/Al₂O₃ reduction curve shown in Figure 3. The low temperature
217 shoulders are attributed to reduction of NiO species with different interaction with
218 alumina, the interaction being weaker for 600 °C-reduced species and stronger for
219 those reduced at 725 °C [31, 32]. Finally, the highest temperature peak at 825 °C is
220 assigned to well dispersed NiAl₂O₄ spinel reduction.

221

222

223

Figure 3. H₂-TPR characterization of the catalysts

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225

226 In conclusion, characterization results evidence that the γ -Al₂O₃ support has
227 much higher surface area than ceria, and NiO seems to be better dispersed on the
228 alumina support than on ceria. However, NiO reduction is improved in the Ni/CeO₂

229 catalyst with regard to Ni/Al₂O₃, with evidences a simultaneous reduction of NiO and
230 surface CeO₂.

231

232 **3.2. Catalytic tests.**

233

234 The catalytic methanation of CO₂ has been studied, and the CO₂ conversion
235 curves are shown in Figure 4a together with CH₄ selectivity profiles in Figure 4b.

237

238 Figure 4. CO₂ methanation catalytic tests. (a) CO₂ conversion and (b) CH₄ selectivity.

239

240 The Ni/CeO₂ catalyst is much more active than Ni/Al₂O₃, with onset CO₂
 241 conversion at 250°C and a progressive increase until reaching the equilibrium curve at

242 375°C. CH₄ is the only reaction product, with 100% selectivity in the whole range of
243 temperatures screened.

244 The catalytic activity of Ni/Al₂O₃ is much lower, with a slow increase in CO₂
245 conversion above 250 °C and without reaching thermodynamic equilibrium
246 conversions in the range of temperatures studied. The CH₄ selectivity is not 100% in
247 this case and CO is also produced together with CH₄, the CH₄ selectivity increasing
248 with temperature from 65 to 90%.

249 These differences in catalytic activity have been already reported by other
250 authors [24, 25], and the higher activity and selectivity of ceria-supported nickel
251 catalysts with regard to Ni/Al₂O₃ has been tentatively attributed to differences in the
252 reaction intermediates created upon CO₂ chemisorption and to the reducibility of ceria.
253 XPS characterization, isotopic experiments and catalytic reactions followed by in situ
254 DRIFTS have been carried out in this study, and results are discussed in the coming
255 sections providing further insights about the role of the support in the Ni-catalysed CO₂
256 methanation.

257

258 **3.3. Fresh and used catalysts characterization by XPS.**

259

260 Changes in the oxidation state of nickel during the catalytic tests were studied
261 by XPS by analyzing the Ni2p energy region for both catalysts before and after the
262 catalytic experiments. Figure 5 compiles the spectra, where important differences are
263 noticed depending on the catalyst support.

Figure 5. Ni2p spectra of the catalysts before and after the catalytic tests.

Ni2p spectra can be deconvoluted in several contributions, but there is not a general consensus about the assignation of these bands. It has been suggested [33-36] that the position of the most intense peak can be used to determine the oxidation state of nickel and to obtain information about the charge density of its cations.

The main peak for the Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst is centered at 855.9 eV, and this energy is consistent with the presence of Ni²⁺ cations, either forming NiO or partially hydrated oxides [34, 35, 37]. The Ni2p spectrum of Ni/Al₂O₃ does not change during the catalytic tests, suggesting that the charge density of the Ni²⁺ cations is the same before and after methanation.

However, the main Ni2p peak for the Ni/CeO₂ catalyst is centered at 854.8 eV, that is, there is a shift of more than 1 eV in the binding energy of this main peak with regard to Ni/Al₂O₃, and this is an evidence of the different NiO-support interaction. The main peak in the Ni2p spectra of Ni/CeO₂ also shows a shoulder at low binding energy (852.2 eV), which indicates the presence of Ni⁰. The coexistence of these two nickel

281 species is very positive for the CO₂ methanation reaction, because nickel oxide species
282 in close contact with ceria are active sites for CO₂ chemisorption and dissociation, and
283 Ni⁰ species are effective sites for H₂ dissociation [38]. This distribution of nickel
284 species, combining Ni²⁺ and Ni⁰, is maintained after the catalytic tests, and this is
285 consistent with the stability of this catalyst previously demonstrated in 24 hours stability
286 tests [39].

287

288 **3.3. Isotopic experiments.**

289

290 The CO₂ methanation mechanisms have been studied for Ni/Al₂O₃ and Ni/CeO₂,
291 and isotopic experiments have been performed with ¹³C¹⁸O₂ pulses in order to
292 understand the role of catalyst oxygen during the reactions. Figure 6 shows results of
293 the first ¹³C¹⁸O₂ pulse performed after a reference Ar pulse for Ni/Al₂O₃ (Figure 6a) and
294 Ni/CeO₂ (Figure 6b). For proper interpretation of the results, note that not all m/z
295 signals monitored during the experiments are plotted in these figures, i.e., those signals
296 with negligible values are not included in Figure 6 for the sake of simplicity.

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300

301 Figure 6. First pulse of Ar and ¹³C¹⁸O₂ at 350 °C over (a) Ni/Al₂O₃ and (b) Ni/CeO₂.

302

303 The Ar profiles provide a reference for both catalytic beds of the shape of an
 304 inert gas travelling through the solid sample without chemical interaction. Most signals
 305 detected once ¹³C¹⁸O₂ is pulsed appear at the same relative time than Ar, considering

306 time = 0 seconds the injection of the gas. These signals include CO₂, CO and CH₄
307 species, which indicates that exchange of oxygens between CO₂ molecules and
308 catalysts, all reaction steps required to hydrogenate CO₂, and the desorption of CH₄
309 and CO occur in a time frame much lower than the seconds scale of the
310 measurements. The main difference between the Ar peaks and peaks of CO₂, CO and
311 CH₄ species is the area, which is lower for reactants and products than for Ar, because
312 they are affected by the reaction conversion. Only the H₂O signals appear delayed by
313 40-50 seconds with regard to the Ar reference, and this evidences that the H₂O
314 desorption is significantly slower than the remaining steps of the mechanism. Note that
315 CO is detected in the isotopic experiments but not in the catalytic tests performed with
316 Ni/CeO₂, because the experimental conditions of both types of experiments are very
317 different with much higher concentration of CO₂ in the catalytic tests than in the isotopic
318 experiments.

319 ¹³C¹⁸O₂ is not detected in the pulse experiments shown in Figure 6, and all
320 oxygen-containing gases measured come with ¹⁶O of the catalysts. The detection of a
321 high ¹³C¹⁶O₂ signal indicates that the double exchange of oxygen atoms between the
322 ¹³C¹⁸O₂ pulsed and the catalysts takes place in a significant extent. ¹³C¹⁶O is also
323 detected, probably because the catalysts are partially reduced by H₂ before the pulse,
324 and part of the oxygens of ¹³C¹⁸O₂ reoxidise the catalysts. The release of ¹²C¹⁶O and
325 ¹²CH₄, with ¹²C, evidences that surface carbon species chemisorbed on the catalysts
326 before the ¹³C¹⁸O₂ pulse are also desorbed and participate in the hydrogenation
327 processes.

328 For a quantitative analysis of the pulse experiments, the area of the different
329 peaks has been calculated and expressed as mass balance. Figure 7 compiles the
330 mass balances of carbon species, including CO₂, CO and CH₄ species, both with ¹²C
331 and ¹³C, for the three consecutive ¹³C¹⁸O₂ pulses performed to each catalyst.

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337

338 Figure 7. Percentage of carbon species in three consecutive pulses of ¹³C¹⁸O₂ at 350
 339 °C over (a) Ni/Al₂O₃ and (b) Ni/CeO₂.

340

341 The carbon species distribution keeps constant for the three pulses fed to
342 Ni/CeO₂, but not for those fed to Ni/Al₂O₃. The release of ¹⁸O-containing species is
343 almost negligible for Ni/CeO₂ (only few ¹³C¹⁶O¹⁸O is detected), while for Ni/Al₂O₃, the
344 ¹³C¹⁶O¹⁸O signal increases progressively at expense of the ¹³C¹⁶O₂ decrease. This
345 means that both catalysts exchange oxygen with the CO₂ molecules, but the exchange
346 capacity of ceria is much higher than that of alumina, as expected. This effect is also
347 observed in the H₂O yielded as reaction product, as observed in the mass balances of
348 H₂O plotted in Figure 8. Only H₂¹⁶O is detected for the three pulses carried out with
349 Ni/CeO₂, while some H₂¹⁸O is observed in the third pulse to Ni/Al₂O₃.

350 As shown in Figure 7, the value of the sum of all CO₂ species is constant in
351 progressive pulses for both catalysts, indicating that the conversions are always the
352 same, and Ni/CeO₂ reaches higher conversions (lower \sum CO₂ values) than Ni/Al₂O₃ in
353 agreement with the catalytic tests.

354 The total amount of CH₄ (¹²CH₄ + ¹³CH₄) yielded as hydrogenation product is
355 higher for Ni/CeO₂ than for Ni/Al₂O₃, which is also in accordance with the higher
356 catalytic activity observed in the catalytic test results. Note that the percentages of
357 ¹²CH₄ and ¹³CH₄ released are equal for Ni/CeO₂ and almost equal for Ni/Al₂O₃, and this
358 evidences the hydrogenation of carbon species (with ¹²C) present on the catalysts
359 before the ¹³C¹⁸O₂ pulses together with those created upon ¹³C¹⁸O₂ chemisorption.

360 ¹³C¹⁶O and ¹²C¹⁶O signals are also observed for both catalysts. This was
361 expected for Ni/Al₂O₃, because CO was also detected in the catalytic tests, but not for
362 Ni/CeO₂. This apparent discrepancy between the catalytic tests and the isotopic
363 experiments is attributed to the different experimental conditions used, CO₂ and H₂
364 being in stoichiometric conditions in the catalytic experiments but not in the pulse
365 experiments with isotopic gas.

366

367 Figure 8. Percentage of H₂O species in three consecutive pulses of ¹³C¹⁸O₂ at 350 °C
 368 over (a) Ni/Al₂O₃ and (b) Ni/CeO₂.

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370

371 These isotopic experiments provide very valuable information about the CO₂
 372 methanation mechanism. It can be concluded that, in a first step, the CO₂ molecules
 373 are chemisorbed on the catalysts and, in most cases, the double C=O bonds are
 374 broken. This involves reduced sites of the catalyst that get oxidized by CO₂. Then,
 375 different reaction pathways can be followed. Part of the oxygens removed upon the
 376 double bonds breaking are replaced by catalyst oxygen and are released as CO or
 377 CO₂, leaving reduced sites on the catalyst again. Simultaneously, part of the carbon
 378 species adsorbed on the catalysts surface are hydrogenated and released as CH₄.
 379 Ni/CeO₂ is get involved very efficiently in these processes, and isotopic experiments
 380 suggest that the highly demanding dissociation of the CO₂ double bonds is significantly
 381 improved by this catalyst. Our hypothesis is that the ceria support is involved in the
 382 dissociation of CO₂. As observed by XPS, the Ni/CeO₂ catalyst combines reduced
 383 nickel with cationic nickel species, and it is postulated that the cationic species are

384 probably stabilized at the NiO-CeO₂ interface while nickel with poor contact with ceria is
385 reduced more easily. This combines reduced active sites for CO₂ dissociation in an
386 oxidized environment located at the NiO-CeO₂ interface, with highly reduced nickel
387 sites suitable for H₂ dissociation. Once ¹³C¹⁸O₂ is chemisorbed and dissociated in a
388 reduced active site at the NiO-CeO₂ interface, the adsorbed ¹⁸O are not necessary
389 removed by H₂ in this particular active site. Probably, these oxygens are transferred to
390 the ceria support using the oxygen vacancies created in this support through ceria
391 oxygen removal by H₂ (yielding H₂¹⁶O) somewhere else on the ceria surface. That is
392 why ¹⁸O is not detected in the isotopic experiments with Ni/CeO₂, because the ¹⁸O
393 atoms left by ¹³C¹⁸O₂ are sent and get lost into the ceria support. This is possible due to
394 the high oxygen and vacants mobility of ceria, while other metal oxides, such as
395 alumina, do not have this option.

396 Ni/Al₂O₃ is also able to promote the dissociation of CO₂, which is evidenced by
397 the detection of ¹³C¹⁶O₂ molecules (with catalyst oxygen), but Ni/Al₂O₃ is not as efficient
398 as Ni/CeO₂. The detection of gas products with ¹⁸O after the first pulse of ¹³C¹⁸O₂
399 indicates that a high proportion of catalyst sites available for the dissociation of ¹³C¹⁸O₂
400 are used in the first pulse. This results also show that the adsorbed ¹⁸O is either
401 removed by H₂ yielding H₂¹⁸O or used in a further pulse to be exchanged with other
402 ¹³C¹⁸O₂ molecule. One of the reasons of the lower activity of Ni/Al₂O₃ with regard to
403 Ni/CeO₂ is that CO₂ dissociation and H₂O formation takes place in the same active
404 sites. As deduced from the shape of the H₂O peaks in the pulse experiments, H₂O
405 desorption is much slower than CO₂ chemisorption and dissociation, and therefore, the
406 slow desorption of H₂O limits further chemisorption and dissociation of other CO₂
407 molecules. On the contrary, the high oxygen mobility of oxygen into the ceria support
408 allows dissociate CO₂ in certain active sites (probably at the NiO-CeO₂ interface) while
409 H₂O is being formed and released somewhere else of the ceria surface.

410

411

412 **3.4. In situ DRIFTS experiments.**

413 In situ DRIFTS experiments were carried out to monitor the nature of the
 414 surface species present on the catalysts under reaction conditions at different
 415 temperatures, and Figure 9 compiles the recorded spectra.

416

417

418 Figure 9. In situ DRIFTS experiments under H₂/CO₂/He at different temperatures. (a)
 419 Ni/Al₂O₃ and (b) Ni/CeO₂. Spectra were recorded after 60 min under reaction conditions

420 at each temperature and a background spectrum recorded at room temperature under
 421 He was subtracted in all cases.

422 The intense double band at 2350 cm^{-1} belongs to gas phase CO_2 , and for easy
 423 identification of the surface species on the spectra, Figure 10 shows a scheme of the
 424 main surface carbon species together with the ranges of wavenumbers active in
 425 infrared [38, 40-45].

426

427

428 Figure 10. Scheme of surface carbon species and adsorption regions in infrared
 429 spectra.

430

431 Important information about the methanation mechanism is obtained from
 432 bands below 1700 cm^{-1} , and the behavior of these bands with temperature is different
 433 for $\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (Figure 9a) and Ni/CeO_2 (Figure 9b).

434 The methanation reaction does not occur at $150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (see Figure 4), and the
 435 positive bands in the spectra of both catalysts evidence accumulation of surface
 436 species at this temperature. $\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ spectrum at $150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ shows bands at 1652, 1430
 437 and 1225 cm^{-1} that can be assigned to bicarbonates, which are created by CO_2
 438 chemisorption on hydroxyl groups. The O-H stretching of these bicarbonates is also
 439 observed at 3625 cm^{-1} . The role of the alumina support in the chemisorption of CO_2

440 was already described by other authors, this step playing an important role in the
441 methanation reaction [2].

442 According to the catalytic tests (Figure 4), the onset reaction temperature is
443 around 250 °C, and the Ni/Al₂O₃ spectra at this and higher temperatures evidence the
444 depletion of bicarbonates and the formation of formates as reaction intermediates. The
445 tiny bands at 3000 and 2900 cm⁻¹ are related to the C–H stretching mode of formates,
446 and the bands at 1588 and 1375 cm⁻¹ correspond to their symmetric and asymmetric
447 vOCO modes. The formation of formates upon CO₂ chemisorption, probably on
448 hydroxyl groups of alumina, is consistent with the kinetic study reported by Hubble et.
449 at. [5] predicting that CO₂ chemisorption on Ni/Al₂O₃ takes place with dissociation of
450 one of the oxygens. The presence of formates under reaction conditions explains the
451 production of CO during the catalytic tests. Formates are created once CO₂ is
452 chemisorbed and partially hydrogenated, and these formates can be further
453 hydrogenated yielding CH₄ or desorbed yielding CO + H₂O.

454 On the contrary, the behavior of Ni/CeO₂ is different. The spectrum of this
455 catalyst at 150 °C shows bands at 1583 and 1297 cm⁻¹, which are consistent with the
456 presence of bidentate carbonates in chelate configuration, and these bands disappear
457 under reaction conditions. These two bands are negative at 250 °C and higher
458 temperatures, which evidences the depletion of carbonates that were present on the
459 samples when the background spectrum was recorded in He at room temperature. A
460 small band is also observed at 1390 cm⁻¹ at 150 °C, and also disappears at higher
461 temperatures. This band can be assigned to monodentate carbonates, and these
462 species should additionally present bands around 1300-1370 cm⁻¹ and 1040-1080 cm⁻¹
463 which are hardly observed in Figure 9b. The absence of surface carbon species on the
464 Ni/CeO₂ catalyst under methanation reaction conditions is consistent with the
465 conclusions of the isotopic exchange experiments, that is, CO₂ is chemisorbed and
466 dissociated on reduced sites of the catalyst and carbon intermediates are not observed

467 by infrared because the carbon left is either desorbed as CO₂ taking oxygens from the
468 catalyst or is hydrogenated yielding CH₄.

469

470

471 **3.5. CO₂ + H₂ reaction mechanism on Ni/CeO₂ and Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts.**

472 As a summary of the conclusions obtained by the different techniques used in
473 this study, Figure 11 shows schemes with our outlook about the main steps of the CO₂
474 + H₂ reaction mechanisms taking place on Ni/Al₂O₃ and Ni/CeO₂.

475 Figure 11. Scheme of the CO₂ + H₂ reaction mechanisms on Ni/CeO₂ and Ni/Al₂O₃
 476 catalysts.

477

478 The Ni/CeO₂-catalysed CO₂ methanation reaction starts with the reduction of
 479 the catalyst. This reduction takes place both at the NiO-CeO₂ interface, creating
 480 reduced sites on an oxidized NiO-rich environment, and on the ceria support creating

481 oxygen vacancies. Among these sites, the NiO-CeO₂ interface is reduced more easily,
482 but the ceria support is much more abundant, and therefore is statistically more
483 accessible to H₂. Additionally, XPS results evidence that part of the NiO particles, those
484 with poor interaction with the ceria support, are reduced to metal nickel where H₂
485 molecules are efficiently dissociated. CO₂ chemisorption takes place on the partially
486 reduced NiO-CeO₂ interface, where CO₂ is dissociated, and oxygens are transferred to
487 the ceria support to restore the oxygen balance. These oxygens move throughout the
488 ceria lattice using the previously created vacancies. This transfer of oxygen from the
489 NiO-CeO₂ interface to somewhere else into the ceria support leaves the active sites at
490 the NiO-CeO₂ interface available for further CO₂ chemisorption. Hence, the H₂
491 reduction of the NiO-CeO₂ interface is not necessary after the chemisorption of every
492 CO₂ molecule since the high oxygen mobility on this catalyst allows the reduction to
493 take place somewhere else on the ceria surface. Isotopic experiments indicate that,
494 upon CO₂ dissociation, the carbon atom either can accept ceria oxygens to yield CO₂
495 again or dissociated hydrogens to yield methane.

496 This mechanism is very effective for several reasons: i) the Ni/CeO₂ catalyst
497 combines two types of active sites efficient for CO₂ and H₂ dissociation, respectively; ii)
498 water desorption is the slowest step of the mechanism, as observed in the isotopic
499 experiments and this product is not necessarily formed on the same active sites over
500 which CO₂ is chemisorbed, i.e., the CO₂ chemisorption sites at the NiO-CeO₂ interface
501 are not blocked by water molecules; iii) the catalyst surface does not accumulate
502 carbon-containing species under reaction conditions, which allows faster chemisorption
503 of CO₂.

504 The Ni/Al₂O₃-catalysed CO₂-H₂ reaction follows a different mechanism, and in
505 this case, the participation of the alumina support is not so relevant. Hydroxyl groups
506 are created by H₂ reduction of the NiO-Al₂O₃ interface, where CO₂ is chemisorbed
507 afterwards. The isotopic experiments indicate that part of the chemisorbed CO₂

508 molecules are desorbed after the CO₂ oxygens are exchanged by catalyst oxygens. In
509 this case, CO₂ oxygens cannot migrate and so, remain wherever CO₂ has been
510 dissociated, being further CO₂ molecules chemisorbed and dissociated in this site once
511 again. The CO₂ molecules that are not desorbed yield formates and water upon H₂
512 reduction, and these formates can react in two ways. Part of these formates are further
513 hydrogenated yielding CH₄ + H₂O and part decompose yielding CO + H₂O, which
514 explains the lower selectivity of Ni/Al₂O₃ observed in the catalytic tests. The handicaps
515 of this reaction mechanism, in comparison to that taking place on Ni/CeO₂ are: i) There
516 are not specific active sites for H₂ dissociation, and molecular H₂ must reduce surface
517 species; ii) all the steps of the mechanism take place on the same active sites, and the
518 slow release of water and the accumulation of surface formates on these sites delay
519 the chemisorption of further CO₂ molecules.

520

521 **4.- CONCLUSIONS.**

522

523 The CO₂ methanation reaction mechanism has been studied for Ni/CeO₂ and
524 Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts, and the following conclusions can be summarized:

525 For both catalysts, isotopic experiments evidence a dynamic equilibrium
526 between gas phase CO₂ and catalyst oxygen, consisting of CO₂ chemisorption,
527 exchange of CO₂ oxygens with the catalysts, and CO₂ desorption. In the presence of
528 H₂, part of the chemisorbed CO₂ is desorbed after oxygens exchange and part is
529 hydrogenated.

530 The higher methanation activity and 100% CH₄ selectivity of Ni/CeO₂ is
531 attributed to the following mechanistic aspects: i) XPS characterization shows that
532 Ni/CeO₂ combines two types of active sites efficient for CO₂ dissociation at the NiO-
533 Ceria interface and for H₂ dissociation on reduced Ni⁰ particles; ii) pulse experiments
534 show that water desorption is the slowest step of the mechanism and, due to the high

535 oxygen mobility throughout the ceria lattice, water is not necessarily formed on the
536 same active sites that chemisorb CO₂, that is, the CO₂ chemisorption sites at the NiO-
537 CeO₂ interface are not blocked by water molecules; iii) in situ DRIFTS experiments
538 show that the Ni/CeO₂ surface does not accumulate carbon-containing species under
539 reaction conditions, which allows faster chemisorption and dissociation of CO₂.

540 The handicaps of the Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst, in comparison to Ni/CeO₂, are: i) There
541 are not specific active sites for H₂ dissociation, and molecular H₂ must reduce surface
542 species; ii) all the steps of the mechanism take place on the same active sites, and the
543 slow release of water and the accumulation of surface formates on these sites delay
544 the chemisorption of further CO₂ molecules. The formation of formates as reaction
545 intermediates results in the production of CO as undesired byproduct, since part of the
546 formates are totally hydrogenated to CH₄ but part decompose yielding CO+H₂O.

547

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562

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